

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FIVE-CYCLE LOAD/UNLOAD AND FULL-CYCLE FATIGUE OF COMPOSITES WITH INTEGRATED RESIN FLOW CHANNEL

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ABSTRACT

Growth of carbon-epoxy reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite material usage is attributed to its advantages over conventional metals, such as specific strength-to-weight ratios and freedom of design. The i series vehicles that are produced by the BMW Group are a prime example of increasing use of composites in a high-volume sector. High-volume manufacturing necessitates faster production techniques, such as high-pressure resin transfer moulding (HP-RTM). The integration of resin flow channels into HP-RTM moulds assists with production of complex parts by reducing total flow resistance, decreasing fill times and guiding the resin through the mould. This research aimed to identify the effects of local geometric features, such as resin flow channels and resulting lamina undulations, on the mechanical performance of CFRP composite laminates. Two types of resin flow channels were investigated; a single large resin flow channel and multiple small resin flow channels. These are compared alongside reference specimens without resin flow channels. While fatigue tests are expensive regarding the time, machinery and labour that are required, they are critical to determining service life. This research explored the possibility of identifying the fatigue endurance limit of these composite laminates without conducting a full-cycle fatigue test. The R and MC specimens showed a strong relationship between fatigue life and five-cycle tests, with service life of up to a million cycles when operated below the peak critical loads. The SC specimens contradicted this, with the fatigue mean loads lower by 52 and 2% than those of the peak critical and acoustic critical loads, respectively. The specimens had both low- and high fatigue life cycles. This behaviour was influenced by the differing lamina undulation and top-ply stitch locations. Overall, a five-cycle-based understanding of fatigue life provided a new insight and possibly a new way of estimating good fatigue service life.

1. INTRODUCTION

BMW's i models represent a medium to large scale production series, and carbon-fibre reinforced composite laminates are a significant constituent of their ground-breaking LifeDrive architecture. The cars' intricate design features involve the use of a carbon-epoxy composite, which is manufactured via a high-pressure resin transfer moulding (RTM) technique and a wet compression moulding method. This effective manufacturing process is both efficient and economical. Hence, significant research has explored both the manufacturing techniques and the performance of composite structures [2-5]. Increased demand for these vehicles necessitates faster manufacturing of composite structures. A common approach to reducing cycle times is the integration of resin flow channel(s) that span from the injection point in the RTM tools [1-4].

The flow channels are a cavity in the mould that facilitates the resin to flow in a particular direction. The distribution system is implemented on the mould surface; this aids in reducing the injection pressure and reducing the tooling costs. The effects of defects on the flow front progression and the accuracy of filling have been investigated by various researchers. The results identified the flow front reaction to a solid obstacle in the flow path [5-7]. The flow channel cross-section size and form are designed and optimised based on fluid shear stress distribution, flow length, part thickness, mass, and volume. A circular cross-sectioned shape seems to be optimum for heated flow channels,

and it is observed that the cross-section size of the optimum flow channel is dependent on the permeability of the textile [8].

Figure 1 presents composite laminates, both with and without resin flow channels. The reference (R) specimens are rectangular composite laminates without any resin flow channels. The single-channel (SC) and multiple-channel (MC) specimens are also called supply and distribution channels, respectively.

Figure 1: Composite laminates both with and without resin flow channels

Intentionally induced manufacturing features and uncertainty that is caused by the design process result in increased testing, which ranges from the lamina level to large-scale structures. These tests are conducted to achieve a level of confidence in the material's system and design.

The load/unload scheme, which is widely used to study damage accumulation and to identify stiffness loss, was first applied in combination with Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring back in the 1950s. Kaiser demonstrated that the AE reinitiates after crossing the previous load level in metallic materials; this behaviour was named the Kaiser Effect [9]. The point on the stress-strain response where the AE events begin to either record or intensify is called the Kaiser Effect point [10]. As reported by Tensi [11], Kaiser's first experimental investigation was conducted on soft carbon steel in 1949 on a pendulum tensile testing machine. Other material systems, such as metals, alloys and wood, have been investigated to identify the Kaiser Effect. He reported that, in metals, the AE is caused by non-homogeneous slip dislocations. However, in brittle rocks, it is caused by the initiation and propagation of micro-cracks [12].

The rock failure mechanism was investigated by Tang and Hudson [13]. A cyclic load/unload scheme was incorporated to investigate damage behaviour. Based on their investigation, there was no AE during the reloading of the specimens until the previous maximum load level is reached. This behaviour represents the Kaiser Effect.

For fibre-reinforced polymers, AE signals were initiated at lower loads than they were for previous loads of a cyclic load/unload scheme [14]. This fundamental observation was made by Fowler [15], who introduced it as the Felicity Effect, which is notably always quantified as a ratio [16]. Based on the fundamental observations, the FR is considered an important concept in understanding the failure evolution of composites using AE. FR is defined as the ratio of load at the beginning of the first significant AE (above threshold) during loading and the previous maximum load.

The Felicity Effect has been studied extensively to analyse the residual strength of composite structures. The higher the FR, the lower the damage, which implies that, when the $FR = 1$, the damage is lower, and an $FR < 1$ indicates permanent damage [17, 18].

This study focused on identifying a possible test strategy based on five-cycle loading, which could provide insight into the fatigue performance of composite laminates with integrated resin flow channels, thereby reducing the cost and time requirements that are typically associated with fatigue testing. The approach is based on the identification of AE-based five-cycle peak loads and acoustic critical loads, which show an acoustic trend that corresponds with the fatigue behaviour of composite laminates.

2. MATERIAL MORPHOLOGY

In the current investigation, two different types of resin flow channels were investigated: (a) single large resin flow channel and (b) the multiple small resin flow channels. The samples were taken from a panel in which one half of the panel was with a resin flow channel, and the other half was without. Figure 2 presents the schematic illustration of the RTM platen of the SC specimens. Two R specimens were chosen from the location that did not have any resin flow channels. The specimens with resin flow channels were cut at different distances from the resin injection point. Specimens P3, P2, and P1 were 15, 70, and 125 mm away from the resin injection point, respectively and the R specimens R1 and R2 were 65 and 150 mm away from the resin injection point, respectively. The MC specimens also had an RTM-similar platen layout.

Figure 2: The schematic overview of a flow channel distribution system

The acronyms of P1, P2, and P3 are specific to the position of the specimen from the resin injection point. The P3 specimens are closer to the resin injection point, and the distance increases with specimens P2 and P1, respectively. The acronym PX_SC refers to the position and the type of the specimens.

In SC specimens, based on the position relevant to the resin injection point, significant variations of the lamina undulations were observed. Figure 3 presents the micrograph of a SC specimen: (a) shows the stacked laminas and single large resin flow channel, (b-c) presents the top lamina undulations, and (d) shows the top lamina stitches present at the interface of top-ply and the resin flow channel. In the MC specimens the lamina undulations were within 1% variations irrespective of their position in the RTM platen, hence all the specimens were just named MC.

Figure 3: Micrographs of variations in the lamina undulation of the SC specimens: (a) Stacking of laminas, (b-c) lamina undulation and (d) top-ply stitches

The lamina architectures of the individual specimens were investigated. Figure 4 presents the variations of the lamina undulations for the top four plies of the composite laminates with integrated resin flow channels. The MC specimens had an average top-ply lamina undulation of 0.023 mm.

The top four plies of the composite laminates in the SC specimens were observed to have significant variations in lamina undulations. Hence, the peak lamina undulation was investigated for

these plies. The SC specimens at the P3 position exhibited the maximum undulations. The top ply had an average lamina undulation of 0.712 mm. Decreases in lamina undulation of up to 42 and 77% were observed in the top ply (0°) for the specimens at the P2 and P1 positions, respectively. P3-SC specimens, at an orientation of 90°, had a lamina undulation of 0.521 mm in the second ply. A 47 and 77% decrease in second ply lamina undulation were observed in P2-SC and P1-SC specimens, respectively. P3-SC specimens had a third ply lamina undulation of 0.293 mm. Decreases in third ply lamina undulation of up to 32 and 89% were observed in the P2-SC and P1-SC specimens. The fourth ply architectural variations showed a lamina undulation of 0.120 and 0.098 mm in the P3-SC and P2-SC specimens, respectively. The P1-SC specimens did not show any lamina undulation at this layer of the composite lamina.

Figure 4: Variation in lamina undulation of the SC and MC specimens

3. AN INVESTIGATION METHODOLOGY

Four-point flexural five-cycle and fatigue tests were used to characterize the mechanical performance of composite laminates with and without resin flow channels (Figure 5) for channel compression. Tests were conducted on an Instron 1186 electro-mechanical universal testing machine at the loading rate of 1 mm/min at room temperature for the five-cycle loading. A support span of 140 mm was chosen to support the applied load at a span of 70 mm from the Instron machine. Vallen AE-suite was used to monitor the damage. The piezo-electric sensors were used to detect and record events. AE sensors were coupled with the specimen using petroleum jelly and connected to the data acquisition system via coaxial cables. The system performance check was conducted by carefully breaking pencil lead on the surface of the test specimens. Fatigue tests were conducted at a load ratio of 0.2 and a frequency of 2 Hz.

Figure 5: Composite laminates both with and without resin flow channels

Monotonically increasing the applied load is a common loading concept in any mechanical testing. Repetitive loading and unloading of cycles are a popular loading scheme for evaluating the AE

behaviour of material systems (ASTM E 1067).

The load/unload sequence was incorporated, as shown in Figure 6. In this loading sequence, the specimens were monotonically loaded until they reached a specific load of 'L₁', followed by fully unloading. In the next cycle, the load was increased until a load level of 'L₂', which was greater than the previous load 'L₁'. This process was repeated five times up to a certain maximum load 'L_{max}' or a failure load of 'L_{failure}'.

Specifically, to obtain a relative comparison between the different specimen types, the failure loads of the R specimens without any resin flow channels were considered the target load. The confidence in the target load was 95%; this was decided based on the standard deviation of the static flexural monotonic tests of the R specimens. Five cycles of load/unload tests were designed based on the set target load of 1.25 N, as shown in Figure 6. If specimens completed all five cycles of the loads, then those specimens were loaded to the point of failure.

Figure 6: Five-cycle load/unload scheme

4. AE PARAMETER-BASED INTERPRETATIONS OF LOAD AND ACCUMULATION OF EVENTS

The developed methodology for five-cycle loading protocol identified the critical damage loads in composites with integrated resin flow channels. The investigation aided in defining a critical acoustic load (LCA), the load at which the specimens violated the Kaiser Effect [149]. Further, five-cycle critical peak loads were measured to compare the load-tend response between tested specimen types. This established interpretation compared and studied the full-cycle fatigue damage evolution. Figure 7 presents the AE historic response, demonstrating the sum of AE events counts-load behavior.

Figure 7: AE historic response of composite laminates with integrated resin flow channels got five-cycle loading protocols: (a) reference, (b) single channel and (c) multiple channel specimen

The total sum of counts was investigated to identify the accumulation pattern. Figure 7.a shows the five-cycle AE cumulative trends of the R specimen. The Kaiser Effect was observed in up to three

cycles of loading; the critical peak load for a R specimen was 750 N. For the first three cycles of loads, the R specimen the AE reinitiates after crossing the previous load level during reloading cycle, this implies that the specimen had a negligible permanent or plastic deformation. During the fourth cycle of loads, the reference specimen sustained damage, and the Kaiser Effect was no longer observed.

New AE events began to occur in the subsequent loadings before the previous peak loads were reached. The critical acoustic load at which the AE events began to occur during reloading was 575 N. This was defined by identifying more than five bursts of AE during a 10% increase in load. Identifying the critical load aids in recognising the beginning of damage progression based on the previously induced damage. AE energies also provided a similar accumulation trend. A dramatic increase in the AE count rate was observed at 575 N. A nonlinear increase in the AE event rate and dramatic variation in the accumulation pattern of the AE events are described in ASTM E 1067 and E 1118. The standards explain that these events in composites are critically intense AE activities that can cause severe damage. This is also the region where the violation of the Kaiser Effect was present to the greatest extent with lower Felicity values.

The total number of AE counts in the SC specimens was less than those in the R specimens (Figure 7.b). The R specimens had three times more counts than the SC specimens for the critical peak load. During the unloading of the first three cycles of loads, AE events were recorded. This indicates that the SC specimens showed the Shelby Effect during the early stages of loading. The Felicity Effect was found after completion of the third cycle. During the loading stages of the fourth cycle, the AE accumulation began at 450 N, which was less than the previous peak load. Compared to the R specimens, a 24% decrease in the critical acoustic load was observed in the SC specimen.

The MC specimens demonstrated different trends compared to the R and SC specimens (Figure 7.c). At the beginning of the first cycle, the specimen had an increase in the number of AE events, with each event having fewer counts, similar to the R specimens. However, the MC specimens had a higher number of counts. There was a much lower accumulation of counts during the second and third cycle of loads compared to the other specimen types. The Felicity Effect was not clearly visible. Nonetheless, the third cycle of loading for 380 N of load had an early accumulation of AE events. Compared to the R specimens, a 40% decrease in the critical acoustic load was observed in the MC specimen. The five-cycle critical peak load for the MC specimen is 500 N, which is 40% less than the other specimen types. A rapid increase in the rate of accumulation of AE events and their total counts was observed after 750 N. This kneeing effect is due to the rapid deformation of the specimen because of its stiffness loss.

For the investigated set of three specimens of the R, SC and MC, a variation of 4, 8 and 9% was observed in the critical acoustic loads. When the applied loads were below critical acoustic loads, the specimens did not sustain any permanent damage and when a structure is operated under this load, it can offer better service without permanent damage.

5. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FIVE-CYCLE AND FULL-CYCLE FATIGUE

Based on the complex fatigue behaviour of composites, the identification of the service life under cyclic loads requires exhaustive efforts. Therefore, this study sought to identify a relationship between five-cycle load/unload and full cycle fatigue performance.

The R specimens had a five-cycle critical peak load of 750 N and a critical acoustic load of 575 N. The reference specimens' fatigue was tested for 80, 70 and 60% of the static flexural loads. Those specimens yielded a fatigue life of million cycles. The mean fatigue loads were below the five-cycle critical peak load and the critical acoustic load. This indicates that fatigue mean load operated in the region where the Kaiser Effect dominates the material acoustic behaviour.

The fatigue life of MC specimens was investigated for 60, 70 and 80% of the static flexural loads. The service life of the specimens increased with the decrease in mean operating loads. Five-cycle load/unload tests revealed that the MC specimens had a five-cycle critical peak load of 500 N and a critical acoustic load of 380 N (Figure 8.a).

Figure 8: Five-cycle load/unload and full-cycle fatigue relationship in MC specimens

At 80% fatigue operating load, the mean loads were above both five-cycle critical peak load and critical acoustic load (Figure 8.a). The specimens at this load level did not exceed a maximum service life of 1000 cycles. Both 70 and 60% of the fatigue mean loads are below five-cycle critical peak load and above critical acoustic load. However, 70% of the fatigue mean load was 5% less to the five-cycle critical peak loads, and it had a maximum service life of 28,000. Notably, as the operating fatigue mean loads approached or were below critical acoustic load, the specimens had a fatigue life of nearly a million cycles.

The SC specimens had a five-cycle critical peak load of 750 N and a critical acoustic load of 450 N. Those specimens were fatigue tested for 60% of the static flexural loads. Although the specimens were fatigue tested below critical acoustic load, the variation in the lamina architecture, such as lamina undulation and the presence of stitches, influenced the fatigue life significantly. This resulted in a varying number of fatigue cycles for the same load (Figure 8.b).

6. CONCLUSIONS

A methodology was developed to estimate fatigue performance based on the five-cycle loading protocols. The Kaiser Effect and the Felicity Effect, which are based on critical acoustic and peak loads, were defined for composite laminates. The reference and multiple-channel specimens that were tested for different fatigue loads revealed a trend for the identified five-cycle critical acoustic and peak loads. These specimens had longer fatigue life (one million cycles) when the operating fatigue loads were closer/below critical acoustic loads for the adapted five-cycle loading protocols. Although all the single-channel specimens were fatigue operated below critical acoustic loads, there were specimens with both low and high fatigue life. For example, P1 SC specimens had a fatigue life of more than one million cycles, and the P3 SC specimens had a minimum of 1,000 cycles. This variation in having different fatigue life can be due to the influence of the local geometric features, such as stitches at the corners of the resin flow channels.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the fatigue behaviour has a relationship with the five-cycle acoustic behaviour, however its also influenced by the local architectural variations such as lamina undulation and stitches. Additionally, the resin flow channels can have a detrimental effect on the flexural fatigue performance on channel compression. Decisions about the number of flow channels and their size and location are needed to consider the specific loading scenario for the actual component because the composite laminates with and without resin flow channels have different failure behaviours.

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